

Research

Temperature (maximum) and Rainfall Prediction Using FNN and RNN Models over Kaba Aye Station, Yangon Region, Myanmar

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Abstract: Rainfall and temperature are essential roles in weather forecasting in a tropical country like Myanmar. In this study, we explored data-driven feed-forward neural networks (FNN) and recurrent neural networks in terms of long short-term memory (RNN-LSTM) utilized for predicting temperature (maximum) and rainfall at Kaba Aye station. We trained both FNN and RNN-LSTM models separately to predict, and explored the models' prediction capabilities. The FNN models are trained with 9 years of monthly data which includes temperature (maximum, and minimum), rainfall, relative humidity, pressure, and nino1.2. Whereas, the LSTM-based RNN model is trained with 9 years of monthly data which includes monthly maximum temperature and rainfall. The result of the outputs was the monthly maximum temperature and rainfall of the next year. respectively. For the given station, the expected monthly maximum temperature and rainfall in each month of 2010 are predicted in this research. The results of temperature prediction show that the RNN-LSTM model provided better results with the mean absolute error (MAE=1.33), mean squared error (MSE=2.57) and root mean squared error (RMSE=1.6). Generally, both FNN and RNN-LSTM models examined overestimate in rainfall, however, the FNN model performed better with (MAE=70.6), and (RMSE=107.08).

Keywords: Maximum temperature, rainfall, feed-forward neural network (FNN), recurrent neural network in terms of long short-term memory (RNN-LSTM), Myanmar

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I Introduction

In a tropical country like Myanmar, the prediction of temperature and rainfall are important and useful for livelihood, agriculture, health, irrigation and ecosystem sectors. Myanmar is highly vulnerable to climate change because it

exists in a tropical region where the temperature rises quickly [1]. Moreover, rainfall variability is among the basic indicators of a region's climate and water cycle changes. Anomalous changes in rainfall dynamics may cause hydrometeorological hazards such as drought, and storms, thus ultimately resulting in the loss of human lives, destruction of biodiversity and natural resources [2]. In addition, the variations in rainfall patterns may also occur on intra-seasonal and inter-annual scales, posing serious threats to agriculture, water resources, and the sustainable development of a region [3]. Therefore, the use of information, science and technology to forecast the atmosphere's condition at a specific location is known as regional weather forecasting. Prediction of the rainfall determines the rainfall conditions over a specific location and it is considered vital for the agricultural industry and other industries of the country [4].

The climate of Myanmar is dominated by the Southeast Asian (SEA) monsoon; about 70% of the total annual rainfall is received during the monsoon season (June to September), with large spatio-temporal variance at the country level across latitude and longitude [5]. The significant changes in the number of heavy rainfall days and the intensity of daily rainfall, demonstrate that locally heavy rainfall is likely to occur over a short time and that more rainfall extremes over the SEA are probable in a warmer future. Such increasing trends in extreme rainfall have been scientifically observed during the last few decades over Asia, and will likely increase further with global warming [6]. It is expected that rainfall intensity shifting and patterns will undergo certain changes, and extreme weather events such as drought and flood may occur more frequently [7]. Such changes have already been experienced over Myanmar, resulting in heavy rainfall and loss of capital, infrastructure, and human lives during 2009 and 2014.

Myanmar is one of the countries all over the world which has been affected by extreme weather events between 1993 and 2012 [5]. Hence, Myanmar is vulnerable to significant climate fluctuations due to climate change. Studies have shown that among all climate variations, the monsoon has the largest seasonal, inter-annual, and interdecadal variability among all monsoon-affected countries. Zin and Zhi (2016) observed that this change may cause changes in rainfall patterns leading to extreme rainfall events such as floods and droughts in the region and the increase in heavy rainfall days between the early 1990s and 2010 in Myanmar was associated with increase in temperature about 0.2 °C [3]. Their study also showed that the years 1994, 1997, 2001, and 2007 were noted to be extreme wet years, while 1983, 1987, and 1998 were extreme dry years in Myanmar. Thus, it is important to make long-term predictions for both temperature and rainfall over the country.

With the rapid development of intelligent systems in recent years, people have gained great convenience in their daily life. Image recognition, object detection, smart recommendation, self-driving cars, and many more neural network technologies have achieved great success in their applications [8]–[11]. However, there are still many applications that can bring great benefits to people lacking corresponding artificial intelligence models. The use of the neural network in weather applications has been applied for various lead times and in different locations [4], [12]–[15]. This included hourly, daily, monthly, quarterly, annually, etc. Many studies have shown that both FNN and RNN-LSTM are applicable for predicting timeseries data, especially RNN-LSTM which is designed for this specific task [16], [17]. The application of neural networks in meteorological forecasting is what we are going to investigate in this study.

China meteorological administration developed a new generation of numerical weather prediction model, the Global/Regional Assimilation and Prediction System (GRAPES) to enhance meteorological services in China and based on GRAPES, different NWP systems were developed for different applications: such as GRAPES mesoscale NWP system (GRAPES-Meso), GRAPES typhoon forecast model (GRAPES-TCM), GRAPES sand storm forecasting model (GRAPES-SDM), and GRAPES global forecasting system (GRAPES-GFS) [18]. The Australian Community Climate and Earth-System Simulator-Seasonal Prediction System (ACCESS), a forecasting model released by the Bureau of Meteorology which can forecast rainfall with a mean absolute value (MAE) of 125.345 and root mean squared error (RMSE) of 179.139, is being used to forecast weather in Australia. Myanmar's meteorology and hydrology department using Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model to predict weather for short and seasonal weather forecast. Weather predictions are created by gathering quantitative information about the atmosphere's current condition and utilizing

scientific knowledge of atmospheric processes to predict how the atmosphere will change. Ali Haidar and Brijesh Verma developed the one-dimensional deep convolutional neural network model to forecast monthly rainfall over a specific location in Australia which performs better in months with higher annual averages with the MAE of 114.654 and RMSE of 158.074 while ACCESS performs better in months with low annual averages [4].

This study aims to predict the monthly maximum temperature and rainfall of Kaba Aye station in Yangon region of Myanmar using two types of machine learning models. We trained neural network models to forecast monthly maximum temperature and monthly rainfall over a specific location in Myanmar namely, the Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) and Recurrent Neural Network based Long Short-Term Memory (RNN-LSTM). The advantage which neural network models has over other weather forecasting methods is that they minimize the error using various algorithms and gives us a predicted value that is nearly equal to the actual value. Such a network is simulated over newer data to find out the weather trend in the future course. To our knowledge, this is the first time applying FNN and RNN-LSTM to predict temperature and rainfall over Myanmar. This study will provide valuable information to weather/climate forecasting department like Department of Meteorology and Hydrology (DMH), Department of Disaster management (DDM) and Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM).

Fig. 1: Location and elevation of Myanmar

II Dataset

This study used observed monthly rainfall, temperature, monthly pressure, wetbulb and relative humidity dataset spanning from 2001 to 2010 for Kaba Aye station in Yangon, Myanmar which is provided by the Department of Meteorology and Hydrology. The selected station is located in Yangon city which is former capital city of Myanmar and also located in the main economic zone as shown in figure 2. Nino1.2 from National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) is also used as training variable for FNN to predict both temperature and rainfall (<https://psl.noaa.gov/data/correlation/nina1.data>). Here, 80% of the whole dataset was used for training the models, 10% for validation, and the remaining 10% for testing.

Fig. 2: Kaba Aye weather station location

III Research Methodology

FNN Model for monthly temperature (maximum) and rainfall prediction

In this work, we considered a feedforward architecture, where all neurons between two consecutive layers are fully connected and the information flows only in one direction, from the input to the output units. A supervised deep feed-forward neural network model under the multilayer perceptron neural network architecture having an input layer, three hidden layers, and an output layer was implemented to forecast monthly maximum temperature and rainfall in this study. Two FNN models were implemented with the first FNN model to predict monthly rainfall with three hidden layers with each layer having 22 neurons. The second FNN model for predicting monthly maximum temperature had three hidden layers with each layer having 128 neurons. One layer of neurons is linked to the following layer in FNN and the measure of how strongly two neurons in neighboring layers are connected is called weight. During the training process, the weights are adjusted according to the training rule being employed, so that the output is closer to the desired result from the given inputs. Rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function (1) is used in both input and hidden layers to map the non-linearity between the input and output of the neural network and to prevent the vanishing gradients issue. Figure 3 show the general architecture of the FNN models in this study. The training algorithm of the proposed FNNs is shown below.

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (1)$$

Algorithm 1 FNN Training Procedure

Input: Training dataset, Validation dataset

Output: Trained FNN

1: Initialize the network weights and bias

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- 2: **For** each epoch:
 - 3: Process the records of the training data cases
 - 4: Compare the actual values to predicted values
 - 5: Calculate the loss function
 - 6: Check the validation dataset
 - 7: **If** better loss values obtained
 - 8: Save the network weights
 - 9: **End**
 - 10: **End**
 - 11: Return the trained FNN
-

Fig. 3: General architecture of the FNN models in this study

Each neural network is trained by updating the connection weights and bias in each layer. The training process continues until reaching a minimum error between the target and the model output values. Then, a forecasting model is obtained. While training, the network performance is measured. The loss function (l) (2) that maps the set of input features into rainfall and temperature was determined as mean squared error:

$$l = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y'_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

The determination of monthly rainfall and maximum temperature values were targeted in this study. To assess the accuracy of the developed models, the measurements that have been widely used in weather prediction tasks were

calculated: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) (3), and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) (4) which are popular metrics to evaluate model performances,

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y'_i - y_i| \quad (3)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n}} \quad (4)$$

RNN-based Long Short-term Memory (RNN-LSTM) for monthly temperature (maximum) and rainfall forecasting

The long-short-term memory (LSTM) is an RNN-based deep-learning method for sequence learning tasks. The main advantage of LSTM networks over other traditional RNNs is their ability to store long-term dependencies using the gating structure, an internal memory unit, that enables them to remember past inputs as they cycle through a feedback loop preventing the output of the neural network from exploding or decaying and to alleviate the vanishing gradient problem. The memory of the past inputs allows the model to better capture and learn temporal patterns in the data. The LSTM frameworks can be used in multiple sequence learning problems such as sequence prediction, text classification, and secondary structure prediction due to their ability to efficiently learn long-term dependencies. As illustrated in Figure 4, typical LSTMs consist of the forget gate (f_t) which controls the flow of information, input gate (i_t), output gate (O_t), and cell state (C). By adapting the flow of information between the cell and each gate through the gating structure, the issues of gradient obliteration or explosion could consequently be diminished.

The calculations of the LSTM model are explicitly described as follows:

$$i_t = \sigma(W_{ix}x_t + W_{ih}h_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_{cx}x_t + W_{ch}h_{t-1} + b_c) \quad (6)$$

$$C_t = C_{t-1}f_t + \tilde{C}_t i_t \quad (7)$$

$$f_t = \sigma(W_{fx}x_t + W_{fh}h_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (8)$$

$$O_t = \sigma(W_{ox}x_t + W_{oh}h_{t-1} + b_o) \quad (9)$$

$$h_t = O_t \tanh(C_t) \quad (10)$$

where σ and \tanh are the sigmoid activation function and hyperbolic tangent activation function, respectively. W is the weight matrix, b is the offset term, and x_t is the input of the current time. h_{t-1} and h_t are the hidden states of the previous time step and current time, respectively. C_{t-1} and C_t are the memory cell states of the previous time and current time.

Fig. 4: Architecture of the RNN-based Long Short-term Memory (RNN-LSTM) Networks

IV Result and Discussions

Climatology of monthly rainfall and temperature (maximum) over Kaba Aye Station

Figure 5 illustrates the monthly mean rainfall and temperature (maximum) over Kaba Aye station during the period of 2001 to 2010. The country has a tropical to subtropical monsoon climate, with three seasons: warm and cool inter-monsoonal (mid-February to mid-May); rainy southwest monsoon (mid-May to late October); and cool and warm northeast monsoon (late October to mid-February) (NAPA 2012). Our result explains that the highest peak of maximum temperature was obtained in the month of April (summer) while the lowest maximum temperature in the month of August (mid monsoon season) as shown in Fig 5. Moreover, the high rainfall received during (may-September) and low rainfall in winter season (November-February). The data is concise to the previous study by Zin and Zhi (2021) explained the maximum rainfall occurred in summer monsoon periods (June – August) over the region [5].

Further analysis of figure 6 explains the annual cycle of rainfall and temperature (maximum) over Kaba Aye station. Fig 6 shows the highest (lowest) rainfall occurred in 2007 (2003). In addition, the temperature (maximum) obtained the highest (lowest) on 2010 (2008) (Figure 6). The figure 6 provides interesting, 2010 year was the hottest year with low rainfall due to climate change.

Fig. 5: Actual monthly Average rainfall and temperature (maximum) from 2001 to 2010

Fig. 6: Actual annual Average rainfall and temperature (maximum) from 2001 to 2010

Observation and models (FNN, RNN_LSTM) for monthly temperature (maximum) on 2010

Figure 7 show the observed and FNN model predicted temperature (maximum) for 2010. The result explains FNN model provided similar value like observed on the month of September, overestimated on April-August, and underestimated on October-March as shown in Fig (7). The comparison of observed and FNN model predicted temperature (maximum) for 2010 is shown in Figure 8. The result presents RNN model provides similar value with observed on December, overestimate on October-November, and underestimate on others month (January-September) (Fig 8). Moreover, table 1 show the mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE) and root mean squared error (RMSE) of FNN and RNN-LSTM models for predicting the monthly maximum temperature of 2010. The result reveal that RNN-LSTM model show less MAE (1.33), MSE (2.57) and RMSE (1.6) than FNN for maximum temperature. Table 2 explain the annual mean, and standard deviation for observed temperature (max), FNN, and RNN-LSTM predictions. The observed mean for 2010 is 34.4 (standard deviation of 2.53), FNN model predicted mean for 2010 is 34.2 (standard deviation of 3.51) and RNN-LSTM predicted mean is 33.4 (standard deviation of 2.39).

Fig. 7: Observed and FNN model predicted monthly maximum temperature of 2010 (°C)

Fig. 8: Observed and RNN-LSTM model predicted monthly maximum temperature of 2010 (°C)

Table 01. Mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE) and root mean squared error (RMSE) of FNN and RNN-LSTM models for predicting the monthly maximum temperature of 2010

Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE
FNN	1.49	3.88	1.97
RNN-LSTM	1.33	2.57	1.6

Table 02. Annual mean, and standard deviation for observed temperature (max), FNN, and RNN-LSTM predictions

	Observed	FNN	RNN-LSTM
Annual Mean	34.4	34.2	33.4
STD	2.53	3.51	2.39

Observed and models (FNN, RNN) for monthly rainfall on 2010

Figure 9 and 10 displays the FNN and RNN model’s predicted monthly rainfall and the observed monthly rainfall on 2010. It is indicated that the pattern of the model prediction and the observed monthly rainfall in 2010 can capture well, however both models overestimated in predicting (Fig 9, 10). However, FNN model performed well with less mean absolute error (MAE) of 70.6, root mean squared error (RMSE) of 107.08 and mean squared error (MSE) of 11467.06 as shown in table 3. In table 4, the rainfall observed mean for 2010 is 207 (standard deviation of 216), the FNN model predicted mean for 2010 is 272 (standard deviation of 290) and RNN predicted mean is 265 (standard deviation of 266).

Fig. 9: Observed and FNN model predicted monthly rainfall on 2010 (mm)

Fig. 10: Observed and RNN model predicted monthly rainfall on 2010 (mm)

Table 03. Mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE) and root mean squared error (RMSE) of two models

for predicting monthly rainfall of 2010

Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE
FNN	70.6	11467.06	107.08
RNN-LSTM	95.3	15712.45	125.35

Table 04. Annual mean, standard deviation of observed rainfall, FNN and RNN-LSTM predictions

	Observed	FNN	RNN-LSTM
Annual Mean	207	272	265

Further analysis of the comparison of observation, FNN, and RNN-LSTM model prediction of monthly temperature (maximum) and rainfall for 2010 can be seen in figure 11 and 12. The results show FNN model provide generally overestimated on (April-September), underestimated on (October-March). But, similar result with observation on (August-September) (Fig 11). RNN-LSTM model give overestimated on (October-December), underestimated on (January-September). However similar result with observation on (August-September) (Fig 11). Figure 12 explain the comparison of observation, FNN and RNN-LSTM models for monthly rainfall on 2010. Generally, both models (FNN and RNN-LSTM) received overestimated rainfall, however RNN-LSTM showed underestimated on (September and October) (Fig 12).

Fig. 11: Comparison of observation, FNN, and RNN predictions on the monthly maximum temperature of 2010 (°C)

Fig. 12: Comparison of observation, FNN, and RNN predictions on monthly rainfall of 2010 (mm)

V Conclusion

In our research, we trained FNN and RNN to predict the monthly maximum temperature and monthly rainfall in Kaba Aye station of Myanmar. Then, we predicted the temperature (maximum) and rainfall of the year 2010 using our trained models. The results show that both FNN and RNN-LSTM can predict the monthly maximum temperature and rainfall of the above-mentioned station. FNN model provide similar with observation on August-September, however, overestimated on (April-September) and underestimated on (October-March). Moreover, RNN-LSTM give similar result with observation on (August-September), overestimate (underestimate) on October-December (January-September). The mean absolute differences between actual and FNN and RNN-LSTM predicted maximum monthly temperature for 2010 is 1.49 and 1.33 and monthly rainfall is 70.6 and 95.3 respectively. Both models (FNN, RNN-LSTM) reveal that overestimated rainfall on May-August, while RNN-LSTM provides underestimated on September-October. FNN model show less error in rainfall prediction as opposed RNN-LSTM explain less error in temperature prediction. Hence overall observations indicate this machine learning model worked well for prediction of maximum temperature and rainfall. The analysis also emphasizes that the prediction performance is good at in seasonal weather forecasting (monthly).

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